

An A to Z of Research Literacy

Edited by: Christine Coombe, Lana Hiasat,
Diana Johnston & Wahida Dastakeer

Research Literacy Glossary

Edited by Christine Coombe, Lana Hiasat, Diana Johnston & Wahida Dastakeer

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Abstract

Abstracts are short paragraphs that are usually found at the beginning of journal articles. They provide a summary of the article.

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A brief summary of a paper that helps the reader quickly ascertain the purpose of the entire paper.

Naziha Ali Raza

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Accidental sampling

Grab sampling, convenience sampling, opportunity sampling

A form of sampling that involves randomly selecting participants from a group that is convenient to reach or access.

Accountability

A central issue in research aimed at promoting ethical research practices through responsibility, integrity and authenticity.

Naziha Ali Raza

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Action research

A type of investigation which is conducted by or in cooperation and collaboration with teachers and other interested individuals in academia. One important objective of action research is to evaluate and assess educational objectives in order to gain a better understanding of its development and implementation. Action research also helps in determining effective ways and means towards achieving outstanding teaching and learning.

Junifer Abatayo

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Action research refers to self-reflective inquiry undertaken with the aim of exploring challenges and/or issues. The aim in action research is to help practitioners develop solutions and be more

development and implementation. Action research also helps in determining effective ways and means towards achieving outstanding teaching and learning.

Junifer Abatayo

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Action research refers to self-reflective inquiry undertaken with the aim of exploring challenges and/or issues. The aim in action research is to help practitioners develop solutions and be more effective at what they care about most - their teaching and the development of their students.

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Aggregate

Combining a lot of parts/elements together.

Mojtaba Chaichi

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Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA)

Short for Analysis of Covariance, ANCOVA is a combination of ANOVA and linear regression. If a researcher wants to study the effect of an independent variable with two or more levels on a continuous variable and further remove the effect of a covariate, then ANCOVA can be the solution. If we would like to study the means differences among three different feedback strategies and their effect on the speaking ability of the learners, we can use ANOVA. However, ANCOVA could help remove the effect of the pre-test as the ANCOVA covariate.

Reza Vahdaniyanavi

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Analysis of variance (ANOVA)

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is a statistical procedure used to compare the mean differences among two or more levels of a categorical independent variable. Some assumptions need to be met to be able to run ANOVA. First, the dependent variable should be continuous. Second, the independent variable should have different levels. Third, the participants should be independent of one another. Fourth, there should not be any significant outliers. Next, the dependent variable should be normally distributed. Lastly, the independent variable should enjoy homogeneity of variances.

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Analytical scale/rubric

To assess productive skills, a table or grid is used with some criteria along one axis and some scores on the other axis. The descriptions in the table cells suggest what the test taker's score is. An example of an analytical rubric is the public version of the IELTS speaking which is available online. Analytic rubrics are often used when the examiners are supposed to give feedback. Holistic rubrics are different from analytical ones in that they do not include a grid for the scoring criteria and only have the scores along one axis. The descriptors in each cell inform raters how they should score.

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Anonymity

Whereby a person's real identity is not revealed in the research. They remain unknown.

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Anonymity implies collecting research data from participants completely unknown to the researchers. It is deemed as central to ethical research practice.

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APA

APA refers to the method of citing an author or referencing a source of information from a book,

Anonymity implies collecting research data from participants completely unknown to the researchers. It is deemed as central to ethical research practice.

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APA

APA refers to the method of citing an author or referencing a source of information from a book, journal or website. E.g. Direct or indirect quoting and source/location of information.

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APA refers to the official style of the American Psychological Association that is used for citing sources of information in educational and social research.

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Applied research

Applied research is a form of inquiry that relies mostly on qualitative methods and that seeks to understand phenomena more than explain and generalize it. It is guided by the belief that in situ analyses offer more potent descriptions of such phenomena than mainstream statistical analyses.

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Applied Research is done by practitioners in the field with the purpose of either solving a problem within the context or obtaining information/data that is sufficient to make a decision pertaining to the problem.

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Assent letters

If a study investigates minors (under the age of 18), a letter of assent must be drafted and signed by the parents and minors. Such letters should include minimally your name, the title of the study, what will be expected of study participants, how long it will take, if they will be compensated or not, how and when they can leave the study, and whom they can contact in case of any concerns. In contrast to the letter of consent, the letter of Assent should be drafted in a language that children can comprehend so they make an informed decision. The letter of Assent is to be submitted to the IRB committee and must be approved by them. Please note that you should supply such letters in the language your participants use. Therefore, the letter may have to be translated. If participants are not literate, they can consent verbally to the letter and you can state this in the signature line. This may apply to very young children. Do not investigate subjects without the written letter of Assent.

Christel Broady

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Attitudinal measures

Refers to the measurement of an individual's emotions, feelings and attitudes. It is used when a researcher wants to gather quantitative data that can be used to measure how someone feels. Researchers can write their own questions or use an existing instrument to measure attitudes. A series of statements are presented to the student and they can express agreement or disagreement. The survey is administered anonymously to encourage student honesty.

Jacqueline Stephen

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Autoethnography

A form of qualitative research in which authors apply self-reflection and writing to explore their personal experience and connect this autobiographical story to wider cultural, political, and social meanings and understandings.

Mojtaba Chaichi

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Axiology

The values and ethics of research

Edith Flahive
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Behavioral observation

Refers to a data collection method employed by researchers to gather information on specific behaviors of an individual. A researcher uses a checklist or a scoring sheet to record observed behaviors. The checklist or scoring sheet consists of a list of behaviors that the researcher will focus on as part of their research.

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Bias

A tendency to show favour towards or against one opinion or one group of people. A biased source does not present both sides of an argument and it is not very objective, reliable or valid.

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Subjective errors in data collection that may cause deviation from 'true' findings and therefore result in unreliable information.

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Bibliography

A list of references referred to but not necessarily cited in the text of a piece of academic writing or a book or an article or a website. It should be in alphabetical order and it is usually found at the end of the work.

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Is the section at the end of a research paper that acknowledges in alphabetical order all the sources consulted while writing that research paper or article.

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Binary data

Binary data is data whose unit takes on only two possible states, traditionally termed 0 and +1 in accordance with the binary numeral system and Boolean algebra. Forms and interpretations of binary data appear in different technical and scientific fields.

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Blinded study

A blinded study is one where the participants and stakeholders in the test do not know who is receiving the treatment, and who is not, so that bias is reduced and results are more reliable.

Eileen Ariza
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Blinded study

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Case study

A comprehensive study that involves in-depth and detailed analysis of a social unit (person, group, or thing) as well as its related contextual conditions and their development over a period of time. This is a popular form of qualitative analysis, the object of which is to locate the factors that account for the behavior patterns of the given unit.

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Causal comparative research

Causal Comparative research is a quantitative way to study the impact of pre-existing causes on effects (retrospective orientation) or pre-existing effects on causes (prospective orientation). The independent variable or the dependent variable is not manipulated by the researcher; the pre-existing condition is brought with the subject to the research study. Thus, the study is about comparing pre-existing conditions and its impact of the outcome.

Christine Sabieh

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Causal hypotheses

A causal hypothesis is a hypothesis that indicates a causal relationship exists between the variables. The statement shows a directional connection; the independent variable under study is what has influenced the dependent variable, causing the outcome. Thus, the result is a direct effect of the variable being manipulated. For example, a sleepy person drinks coffee (caffeine) to stay awake (alert) in order to study for an exam.

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Central tendency (measures of)

Central tendency is a typical value for a probability distribution. There are three measures of central tendency: the mean, the median and the mode. The mean is obtained by adding all the values and dividing that result by the number of values input (i.e. the mean is the average). The median is obtained by writing up all the values in numerical order. If there is an odd number of values, the one in the middle is the median. When there is an even number of values the median is the mean of the two central numbers. Finally, the mode is the value that appears most often in a numerical sequence. If there are no repeated numbers, then there is no mode.

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Chi-square

A chi square statistic is a measurement of how expectations compare with results. The data used in calculating a chi square statistic must be random, raw, mutually exclusive, drawn from independent variables and drawn from enough samples; e.g., the results of tossing a coin 100 times meets these criteria.

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Citation

The method of citing sources of information within an academic paper. E.g. Direct and indirect citations to show where the information came from.

Andrew Johnston

times meets these criteria.
Mojtaba Chaichi
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Citation

The method of citing sources of information within an academic paper. E.g. Direct and indirect citations to show where the information came from.

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A citation is a reference to a published or unpublished source that was consulted and obtained from while writing one's research paper. It is a way to tell the readers that certain material in one's work has come from another source. The in-text or reference list citation contains information like the authors name, title, publication date etc. listed using a specific formatting guideline. There are numerous ways to reference and some of the available styles are APA, MLA, Chicago, Harvard, etc. Citations allow readers to identify and locate original sources that were referred to and helps to strengthen the claim with valid evidence. It also honors the other researchers whose contributions were helpful besides protecting oneself from plagiarism.

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Clinical research

Clinical research is a division of healthcare science that deals with medicines, medical devices, products used for diagnosis and treatment plans for human beings. The main focus of this type of research is to assess the safety and efficacy of those medicines or devices. This type of research can be used to diagnose, find treatment or ease symptoms of a disease.

Doaa Hamam
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This is research into the development of linguistic disorders. Acquired language disorders mainly manifest themselves in late childhood or early adulthood, while developmental disorders have an earlier onset. Lisps, and stuttering, can be easily recognized, and may respond well to speech therapy. Dyslexia, by contrast, may go unrecognized for some time.

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Cluster sampling

Cluster sampling occurs during research. A sample population is divided into certain groups. Each group is a cluster. A random group is selected for the research, and this is called a cluster sampling. A cluster sampling is the group to be studied within the population.

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Coding

A process in which qualitative or quantitative data is categorized for analysis purposes.

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Coding systems

A coding system refers to a system of signals used to represent letters or numbers for transmitting messages.

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Coefficient of Determination

This coefficient is the squared value of the correlation coefficient. For example, for a correlation estimate of .80, the coefficient of determination would be .80 squared, or .64. This value indicates the proportion of shared variance between the two variables involved. Moving the decimal point two places to the right allows for interpreting the overlapping variance between the

Coefficient of Determination

This coefficient is the squared value of the correlation coefficient. For example, for a correlation estimate of .80, the coefficient of determination would be .80 squared, or .64. This value indicates the proportion of shared variance between the two variables involved. Moving the decimal point two places to the right allows for interpreting the overlapping variance between the two variables in percentage terms (e.g., 64% in the above example)

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Cohort analysis

Cohort analysis is a subset of behavioral analytics that takes the data from a given dataset and rather than looking at all users as one unit, it breaks them into related groups for analysis.

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Concurrent data collection

Concurrent data collection/research design is typically employed under mixed methods research. Two types of data (quantitative and qualitative) are collected at the same time. The two types of data inform the study but may not be intertwined as they may answer different research questions within the study.

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Confidentiality

Confidentiality means not disclosing or discussing any information provided by a particular subject that might reveal his/her identification. All the subjects are assured that any data collected will be held in confidence which is agreed upon at the beginning of the data collection process.

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Confounding variable

Third variable; Mediator variable

The confounding variable is a variable that influences the independent variable and affects the dependent variable, producing a spurious causal relationship. The outcome is not caused by the independent variable but by the variable that was not manipulated or considered for study – the confounding variable. Thus, the confounding variable may be a threat to internal validity.

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Consent

A Consent letter is a means of obtaining permission from the participants who have been asked to take part in the research study.

Connie Mitchell

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All researchers should create a letter of consent that should be signed by the adult individuals participating in a study. Such letters should include minimally your name, the title of the study, what will be expected of study participants, how long it will take, if they will be compensated or not, how and when they can leave the study, and whom they can contact in case of any concerns. The letter of consent is to be submitted to the IRB committee and must be approved by them. Please note that you should supply such letters in the language your participants use. Therefore, the letter may have to be translated in several languages. If participants are not literate, they can consent verbally to the letter and you can state this in the signature line. Do not investigate

All researchers should create a letter of consent that should be signed by the adult individuals participating in a study. Such letters should include minimally your name, the title of the study, what will be expected of study participants, how long it will take, if they will be compensated or not, how and when they can leave the study, and whom they can contact in case of any concerns. The letter of consent is to be submitted to the IRB committee and must be approved by them. Please note that you should supply such letters in the language your participants use. Therefore, the letter may have to be translated in several languages. If participants are not literate, they can consent verbally to the letter and you can state this in the signature line. Do not investigate subjects without the written letter of consent.

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Control group

The group in an experiment or study that does not receive treatment by the researchers and is then used as a benchmark to measure how the other tested subjects do.

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Control variable

A control variable is the investigational component which is constant and unchanged throughout the course of the research and investigation.

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Convenience sampling

It is selecting a sample of participants for a research study that is out of ease like the students from the institution that a person is employed or a group of faculty from the same department or institution.

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Conversation analysis

The scientific study of spoken discourse to understand patterns of communication from one setting to another to further understand the impact of social interaction.

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Corpus research

A large body of text is looked at (through computer analysis) in order to study language within real world usage. Data can be ascertained by looking at how the language is used within a large sample

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Correlation

A technique in quantitative research where the researcher looks for a relationship between variables in quantitative data. A correlation coefficient is the main result of a correlation between variables.

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When two or more things are connected, or show to be mutually related, it is called a "correlation."

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Correlational design research

When two or more things are connected, or show to be mutually related, it is called a “correlation.”

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Correlational design research

Correlational design research is a quantitative way to study relationships; it is to determine if variables are related and, if they are, it is to explore what is the degree of the relationship.

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Credibility

Credibility in research is one of the major criteria of qualitative research. Credibility deals with the research findings and how credible, comprehensive and well-developed they are.

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Critical research

Critical research is when research is done with a critical lens. That requires reading multiple sources of readings that deal with the same topic and being able to critique them.

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Critical research is a break from the interpretive and positivist approach towards research that aims towards bringing about a change and emancipating people from the shackles of hidden power structures that distort their social situations. Critical research in language education requires to set up a critical agenda that ensures fairness and equality in curriculum, learning and teaching, and assessment.

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Data

Data is a collection of facts and statistics, that are put together for reference or analysis

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Data analysis

It is the process or procedures employed to review and evaluate data in order to develop a framework or contribute to the current literature the findings from a research study.

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Data collection

Researchers systematically gather information in order to measure a predetermined objective, usually with variables (known or unknown), for the purpose of being able to answer research questions and offer evaluative outcomes.

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Data display

The manner in which data is presented. This could be visually or in text.

Saleh Al-Busaidi

questions and their evaluative outcomes.
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Data display

The manner in which data is presented. This could be visually or in text.

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Data protection

Data security is the process through which data is kept from loss, damage or unauthorized use.

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Data reduction

Data reduction is the transformation of numerical or alphabetical digital information derived empirically or experimentally into an ordered and simplified form. The basic concept is the reduction of multitudinous amounts of data down to the meaningful parts.

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Data-driven

An adjective which means that conclusions, decisions and actions are made based on evidence rather than intuition.

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Decision making

A mental process that involves analyzing information/data, assessing alternative options and then taking a certain course of action.

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Decontextualization

To remove or take something from a context.

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Dependent variable

It is the factor that is measured in an experiment or research study.

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Descriptive research

Research that is concerned with describing the characteristics of individuals, objects, systems or phenomena. It can employ either qualitative or quantitative methods.

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Descriptive statistics

Statistical techniques which allow the population for which data has been acquired to be described. These statistics will often be simple averages but may also involve measures of dispersion. This approach to statistics does not lend itself to any inferences being made.

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Destruction of data

As a researcher, you have to keep your data for a while in case another researcher may want to verify your outcomes. In the past, there have been cases where outcomes were questioned and an audit had to be conducted. You should store your data in a way that it protects the privacy of

Destruction of data

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Deviation

A difference from the normal practice or belief. In statistics, deviation shows how spread out the values are from the mean.

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Diary study

A form of research used to collect qualitative data from participants during a defined reporting period. Participants maintain a diary and are requested to log specific information over time.

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Dichotomous Variables

Dichotomous variables are nominal measures of characteristics or descriptors that have two options, categories, or levels. For example, the gender of a person is male or female; the height of a person is short or tall; the economic status of a person is categorized as rich or poor.

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Direct quote

As a way of avoiding plagiarism, a direct quote is where we cite the exact words that another author used in his/her published work. This type of in-text citation is a way to give credit to the author by including the author, date, and exact page numbers where the words appeared.

According to APA citation rules, if the quoted words are fewer than 40 words then quotation marks should be used. If more than 40 words are quoted, then a block quotation is used.

Researchers may have to pay a permissions fee for using longer direct quotes from other authors to include in their work.

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Discourse analysis

It is the scientific study of language used in any given social context. It tries to analyze the role of discourse in society. (Discourse is language that is used in a specific context. Wherein, the context helps determine the meaning of the actual language used in a particular discourse event.)

It is a research framework or approach that utilizes different tools (conversational analysis, critical discourse analysis, pragmatics, speech act theory, genre analysis, interactional sociolinguistics etc...) to answer a particular problem or research question.

Connie Mitchell
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Discrepant case sampling

Discrepant case sampling is a method of sampling that selects certain cases or samples that are related to a certain theory. The objective is to choose specific cases that may help to make modifications to the theory, confirm, disconfirm or offer clarifications. It is usually used at the last phase of a study after data collection and analysis.

Doaa Hamam

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Doaa Hamam

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Dispersion

Also known as variability and spread, dispersion tells us how far or close a set of scores stand from one another. The commonest forms of dispersion are range, variance and standard deviation.

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Distribution

Distribution is the dispersion of qualitative or quantitative values in a data set based on frequency. The distribution can be shown in a table or in any other graphic forms.

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Document analysis

A form of qualitative research in which documents are interpreted by researchers to give voice and meaning around an assessment topic. Analyzing documents incorporates coding content into themes similar to how focus group or interview transcripts are analyzed.

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Empirical research

Empirical research is when researchers test a hypothesis using direct or indirect observation, instead of just a belief. Data are measurable, and conclusions are drawn based on the results of this kind of measurement.

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Epistemology

This Greek philosophical term is the study of knowing. Researchers are often asked about their epistemological (science of knowing) and ontological beliefs (science of being) because their research perspective and analysis are guided by these beliefs. Researchers have to explain how they came up with knowledge in their study; for example, evidence from participants, field notes, etc.

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ERIC

ERIC is an acronym for Education Resources Information Center. It holds a wide variety of journal articles and publications about educational topics. This is a database of an online digital library, operated by the Institute of Education Sciences of the United States Department of Education.

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Ethics

The study of standards of conduct and moral principles that govern a person's behavior or the conducting of an activity

Education.
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Ethics

The study of standards of conduct and moral principles that govern a person's behavior or the conducting of an activity.

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Ethical Research

As a researcher you become part of the knowledge creators of the profession overall. As such, you have the obligation to conduct research and publish your findings in a way that holds up to scrutiny. Therefore, you should clearly state and follow a respected research methodology that allows the findings to be reliable, generalizable, and applicable to others. Also, your work should hold up to audit by another person who would arrive at the same conclusions as you do. Another part of ethical research is to respect the safety and privacy of humans with whom you work. At all costs, you need to protect their safety, their data, and their privacy. Ethical research projects are usually approved by the IRB and have undergone a rigorous review process. A researcher then has to implement the project as it was approved without any modifications. If modifications are necessary, they must be approved by the IRB again.

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Ethnography

Ethnography started as part of anthropology and dealt with the study of human behavior within a society in an everyday environment. Virtual ethnography follows the same principles of contemporary ethnography but the research field is over online systems.

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Ethnomethodology

The term's meaning can be broken down into three parts: ethno – method – ology, which can help when trying to define it. Ethno refers to a particular socio-cultural group; method refers to the methods and practices the particular group employs in its everyday activities and ology refers to the systematic description of these methods and practices.

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Evaluation research

Research findings are written up either in dissertations or in papers which are published in peer reviewed journals. Strict criteria are applied to such research before it is regarded as acceptable. The process of applying these criteria is sometimes referred to as the evaluation of research.

Research which has not been subjected to peer review or evaluation is generally not considered to be of much value.

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Experiment

An experiment is a method to scientifically study a topic and gather data to understand it; steps define the process in which a researcher manipulates variables to study the outcome of the influence. Throughout the procedure, the researcher collects data to interpret, comprehend, and explain the results. Usually an experiment is conducted to explore or discover phenomena and/or test hypothesis and relationships.

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Experimental research

influence. Throughout the procedure, the researcher collects data to interpret, comprehend, and explain the results. Usually an experiment is conducted to explore or discover phenomena and/or test hypothesis and relationships.

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Experimental research

Experimental research is a type of research design where the researcher controls the variables that may affect the outcome. This may include, for example, subjecting participants to some kind of treatment.

Experimental research is carried out in order to study the relationship between one variable and another.

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Expert sample

This is a term that refers to research conducted using the opinions of people who are known to have a high level of skill or knowledge. This can be determined by using a set of criteria and basing the sample only on those who achieve high scores.

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Exploratory research

Exploratory research is a type of research done to gain further insight about a problem that does not yet have answers or clear definitions. It explores the topic, but may not result in conclusions; however, it may offer further findings to study.

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Extreme case sampling

A type of non-probability sampling that involves a researcher selecting cases that are unusual in one way or another to an extreme, such as outstanding success or a notable failure. An example of extreme case sampling is the study of students who excel in online learning and successfully earn a degree through distance learning. The study can aim to identify specific achievements and characteristics that led to their overall online degree completion.

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Factor analysis

A multivariate statistical technique which is used by researchers in order to identify how it is possible to understand different variables as part of more comprehensive factors or supra-variables.

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Falsification

The action of falsifying information or a theory.

Mojtaba Chaichi

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Field notes

Field notes refer to notes taken by the researcher during a field study as evidence of the behavior or phenomenon being observed. Field notes can be taken during or after the observation. The notes are then analyzed for meaning.

Saleh Al-Busaidi

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Field research

Field research is defining a systematic way to study a topic or problem in a natural setting. Field research may include involving the researcher spending considerable time in the field collecting qualitative data to answer research questions. Field research varies depending on the discipline of study and the research design. To study the effectiveness of introducing a new teaching tool in the classroom, a researcher may form a focus group with the teachers to collect data; through discussions on the effect of the teaching tool on their teaching or on their students' learning, the researcher will be able to gather information to determine the value of the teaching tool.

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Field study

A field study is a research project that involves observing subjects (for example, students) in their natural context (for example, the classroom), rather than in an unnatural context such as a laboratory.

Peter Davidson

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Focus group

A group of people brought together to discuss a particular product or topic. They comprise a diverse group which can be extrapolated to represent a larger segment of the population. They answer open, closed or ranking questions and the moderator of the group may also observe body language and facial expressions in order to gain more insight into the opinions of the group.

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Frequency

The number of times an action or event occurs. This is normally represented in a quantitative form.

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Generalizability

It is applied by researchers in an academic setting. It can be defined as the extension of research findings and conclusions from a study conducted on a sample population to the population at large.

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Grounded theory

It is an inductive methodology. Although many call it a qualitative method, it is not. It is a general method. It is the systematic generation of theory from systematic research. It is a set of rigorous research procedures leading to the emergence of conceptual categories.

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Holistic scale/rubric

As opposed to the analytical rubrics, holistic rubrics have the scores appointed for test takers' performance along one axis. In other words, the scoring criteria or sub-constructs do not appear along another axis, but rather show themselves in the descriptors in each of the grid, or table cells. Normally, holistic rubrics are used when the examiners do not want to give feedback to the test takers. It is advantageous to use an analytical rubric in that it takes less time to assign one single score for the performance than one single score for each scoring criteria, which needs to be added and possibly calculated further for the mean score.

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Human subjects

Human subjects are living people who are being studied in any research project. They are often referred to as participants or subjects.

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Hypothesis

A hypothesis is a proposed supposition or explanation for some kind of phenomena or event to direct investigation into that matter and direct the fact finding mission in order to accept or refute the conclusions.

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Hypothesis testing

In order to accept or refute a hypothesis, it has to go through scientific testing of that hypothesis. This testing goes through four basic steps as follows: 1. identify the hypothesis or phenomenon to be tested; 2. select a specific standard upon which the hypothesis being tested is true or not; 3. choose a random sample from the population being tested and measure the sample mean; 4. compare what is observed from the sample to what was expected if the claims being tested were true.

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Idiographic

Idiographic study is small sample research or unique event research and is sometimes referred to as being idiographic. Thus, the use of a small number of case studies could be referred to as an idiographic study.

Dara Tafazoli

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Independent variable

A variable which is supposed to have an effect on another variable which is called the dependent

as being idiographic. Thus, the use of a small number of case studies could be referred to as an idiographic study.
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Independent variable

A variable which is supposed to have an effect on another variable which is called the dependent variable. This type of variable is the one that is changed or manipulated by the researcher

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Indirect quote

Indirect quote is when you repeat something someone said, only indirectly. E.g: Tom said that he would go, as opposed to saying, Tom said, "I will go." For research purposes, it is often a paraphrased statement whereby only the idea from the original author is cited.

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Inductive

Inductive is characterized by the process of inferring broad or general laws from specific or particular occurrences.

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Inferential statistics

Inferential Statistics are different tests of significance used to analyze data collected from samples to have the researcher interpret the relationship of the variables studied to make predictions about the population the samples were drawn from. The tests of significance include parametric and nonparametric measures that differ based on scales.

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Informed consent

Informed consent occurs when the people being studied are told about the goals and activities of a study and are willing to take part in the research. In studies involving minors, both the children and their guardians must usually agree to the child's involvement.

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Innovation

The process of turning ideas into solutions and implementing these for the enhancement of learning and teaching

Hayo Reinders
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Inquiry

An inquiry is the process that continually aims at acquiring new knowledge or integrating old knowledge, making connections, resolving uncertainties, solving a certain problem or making a decision.

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Interview

Interviews are used to collect data from individuals through oral questioning. An interview can yield data about individual feelings, thoughts, or behaviors. Interviews can be structured, semi-structured or unstructured.

Jacqueline Stephen
Mercer University Atlanta, GA USA

Interview

Interviews are used to collect data from individuals through oral questioning. An interview can yield data about individual feelings, thoughts, or behaviors. Interviews can be structured, semi-structured or unstructured.

Jacqueline Stephen

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In-text citation

An in-text citation formally gives credit to the sources cited in a written document and makes it easier for readers to find the source in a citation or reference list.

Jacqueline Stephen

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Introspection

The process of introspection is done by the researcher on various aspects of the research such as what do the results of the research actually mean. Reflection is also used to explore the motives of the researcher and the choices which have been made during the research process.

Researchers sometimes reflect on the future use of their findings although in general it is sometimes said that not enough attention is given to this aspect of research.

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IRB

Any research that is undertaken in your role as a member of an organization such as a university must be approved by the organizational Institutional Review Board or IRB. The board consists of members whose responsibility it is to ensure ethical treatment of subjects (quantitative) or participants (qualitative). The researcher(s) must complete an institutional IRB application. The IRB committee represents the law on a campus. Minimally, an IRB application includes the title of the project, the researcher(s) names, list of the participants, a statement if the research is exempt, expedited, or needs to undergo a full review, the research methods, data analysis methods, protection of the participants, privacy protection, data destruction policies, and more.

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Likert scale

A Likert Scale is a commonly used psychometric scientific research scale that utilizes questionnaires in its inquiry. The scale is named after its creator, the renowned psychologist Resins Likert. Respondents of a survey which uses Likert scale survey questions respond to statements as to what extent they agree or disagree with them.

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Limitation

Research projects may have limitations due to different factors. Research limitations are usually caused by sample size, lack of previous studies, formulation of research questions, scope of the research study, and implementation of data collection method(s), amongst other factors. Sample size depends on the nature of the research problem. If sample size is extremely small, statistical tests might not reflect and identify significant relationships within a data set. Lack of previous studies is another limitation which research projects may have, especially if a research project is unique in many ways. A third limitation can be caused by research questions which have not been well formulated. The scope of the research study may also be another limitation if the research project is too specific in terms of objectives, implementation duration, variables, subjects, and so on. Lastly, implementation of data collection method(s) can be regarded as a major limitation if the nature of the data collection method implementation is flawed.

Suhair Al Alami

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Suhair Al Alami

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Linear regression

Regression allows the prediction of a dependent variable (e.g. grades achieved on a test) when values are known for independent variables (e.g. time spent studying). Simple linear regression concerns one dependent variable and one independent variable. The relationship between the two variables is charted by plotting a line of best fit in packages such as SPSS. The model which predicts the dependent variable is attested by analyzing the R-squared values of the model. The higher the R-squared value, the more the independent variable is able to predict and account for the variation in the dependent variable.

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Literacy

Most people today understand literacy as the ability to read and write a language. It should be noted this definition presupposes that the reader/writer also understands (and typically speaks) the language to some degree. Certainly, teacher education for literacy prepares teachers with means to teach learners to read and write effectively. Some essential literacy skills include phonemic awareness (i.e., activities for hearing and playing with the individual sounds of language, to create new words using those sounds in different ways) phonics, print awareness, spelling, fluency, vocabulary, reading comprehension, and composition.

Brock Brady

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Literature review

A literature review is a systematic review of various sources about the same topic. It is a critical part of the research process and it may report findings about a specific topic, within a specific amount of time.

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It is a summary report of specific literature which evaluates the author's views on their findings.

This literature review supports the researchers focus on their topic.

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Longitudinal research

This is a research design that involves gathering data by repeated observations of variables over periods of time. The periods of time will vary according to research purposes.

Aidan Thorne

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Mean

Also see Central tendency (measure of). There are several different types of mean used in statistics. The arithmetic or simple mean is the average of a set of numbers calculated by adding up all the numbers and then dividing by how many numbers there are. For example: 4, 8 and 12 would have a mean of $(4+8+12)/3 = 9$. The mean = 9.

Mean

Also see Central tendency (measure of). There are several different types of mean used in statistics. The arithmetic or simple mean is the average of a set of numbers calculated by adding up all the numbers and then dividing by how many numbers there are. For example: 4, 8 and 12 would have a mean of $(4+8+12)/3 = 8$. The mean = 8.

Phil Quirke

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When analyzing data, the mean is the arithmetic average. It is calculated by adding a set of numbers and then dividing by the total numbers of the set. Adding ages in a classroom: 15, 16, 17. $15+16+17= 48 \div 3 = 16$ is the mean

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Median

Also see Central tendency (measure of). The median is the middle number in a sorted list of values. To find the median put all the numbers in numerical order. If there is an odd number of results, the median is the middle number. For example: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5. The median is 3. If there is an even number of results, the median is the mean of the two central numbers. For example: 1, 2, 3, 4. The median is 2.5

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Meta-analysis

Meta-analysis aims to produce a regular pattern or relationship in the findings of the studies in a specific field of research. It analyzes data and findings of different research studies on a specific and well-defined topic to come up with a trend of relationship. Simply put, it involves the combination of the findings of the related studies to estimate the effect of one variable on another related variable.

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Metacognition

Metacognition is the process by which one thinks more deeply about their thinking. In critical thinking it is thought to be "thinking about thinking without thinking." The awareness of one's thinking and the processes by which they employ to solve problems becomes automatic and a matter of habit. Just like riding a bicycle, one doesn't think about the process of how the bicycle is ridden but does it automatically without thinking.

Sufian Abu-Rmaileh

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Methodological framework

A methodology is a set of principles, tools and practices we use to guide our research process. A framework is a loose structure which allows other practices and tools to be included but provides parameters the researcher will adhere to.

Any research will require different methods be employed at different stages and finding the appropriate sequence of methods is often one of the most difficult design steps for any researcher. Therefore, the sequence of methods, which is the methodological framework, needs to evolve and be refined throughout the research process.

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Methodology

It is the systematic, theoretical analysis of the methods applied to a field of study.

Wahida Dastakeer

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This section of research describes the method on how the data will be collected. Techniques and procedures of gathering information are described in this section.

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This section of research describes the method on how the data will be collected. Techniques and procedures of gathering information are described in this section.

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Mixed Methods

Research that uses mixed methods combines quantitative and qualitative analysis, for example, a study using numerical data gathered from test scores and themes derived from interviews.

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Mode

When analyzing data, mode refers to the number that appears most often. Mode in numbers: 1, 3, 5, 7, 7, 9, 15, 21. 7 is the mode.

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Also see Central tendency (measure of). The mode is the value that occurs most frequently on a set of data. For example, in the data set (4, 1, 7, 4, 4, 3, 7, 1, 4) the mode is 4, because this number occurs the most often.

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Moderator variable

Moderator variables are variables that may influence results in a study but they are not the main variable being investigated. For example, in a study of peer review influencing writing gains, a moderator variable may be proficiency level or gender.

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Narrative inquiry

A form of qualitative research in which narratives or stories about the subject of the research are collected and analysed holistically.

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Naturalistic data

Naturalistic data is the data recorded through naturalistic observation that is a research method involving the research subjects in their natural environment. Naturalistic data may be audio or video recording or the researcher's detailed observation notes.

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We use naturalistic data when we want to observe our subject in a natural environment, without any manipulation from the observer. It can be field work or simply recording a speech.

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Negotiation

It is a discussion with the goal of achieving agreement.

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Negotiation

It is a discussion with the goal of achieving agreement.

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Nominal data

Nominal data is symbolic designated data, assigned category measurement that is discrete based on finite sets of values that cannot be divided into parts. Nominal data is the lowest level of measurement scale data. Nominal data may classify people or objects.

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Nominal variable

A Nominal variable, also known as a categorical variable, is a variable with no numeric value. For example, an occupation or a political party would be nominal variables as are race, gender and colour.

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A nominal variable is part of a measurement scale when collecting data (nominal, ordinal, interval and ratio). It is a way of categorizing (labeling or naming) variables.

How old are you? (age)
What is your ethnicity? (nationality, culture, language...)

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Non probability sampling

This refers to the creation of a subset from a sample population based on the researcher's subjective judgement, or because the members of that subset are easily available. This means that not all members of the sample population have the same chance of being selected.

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Null hypothesis

In hypothesis testing a researcher establishes a hypothesis which is a claim which could be correct given that the theory on which it is based is correct. The researcher then attempts to reject this claim or hypothesis. It is important to note that there is never an attempt to prove a null hypothesis.

The hypothesis being tested is referred to as the Null Hypothesis and if it is rejected then the researcher agrees to accept the alternative hypothesis.

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A null hypothesis assumes that there is no significant difference between research samples or populations. It therefore assumes that any difference that is observed can only be the result of an experimental error, or a failure in sampling.

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Numerical analysis

The branch of mathematics that deals with the development and use of numerical methods of solving problems.

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Numerical analysis

The branch of mathematics that deals with the development and use of numerical methods of solving problems.

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NVIVO

NVIVO is a qualitative research software package that is widely used by researchers for data analysis purposes.

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Observation

An observation is a data collection process that is valuable because it can focus on performance and interactions. In education contexts, observations are commonly used to evaluate an instructor's teaching, or to learn how a student (or students) interacts in classroom settings.

Observations may be more descriptive and narrative, for example, how do students respond in interactions (as when the instructor gives additional wait time,) or they may be evaluative as they are when they are used to rate or give feedback on an instructor's teaching competency.

Observations have the benefit of the observer being able to describe the student and teacher behaviors which the observed teacher cannot fully attend to as she is conducting the class

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Observational protocol

A form that is designed and utilized by qualitative researchers to record information they see during an observation activity. Using the form to conduct the observation ensures that the observer is focused on the elements that he/she is required to observe.

Jacqueline Stephen

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One-way ANOVA

One-way ANOVA is used to discover whether there is any significant difference in the means of two or more levels of an independent variable. For instance, if we would like to find out whether three methods of error correction (metalinguistic, reformulation, error-coding) affect EFL learners' writing proficiency differently, we might use one-way ANOVA. This statistical procedure informs us whether there is any significant difference among the means. However, we need to find out where the difference lies, using some other follow-up statistical procedures.

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Ontology

The philosophical study of the nature of existence or being focusing on questions such as; "What things exist?", "Is there such a thing as objective reality?"

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Concerns the nature of the researched world. Someone starting a piece of research always makes some ontological assumptions about what is being researched—for example, that there is a "truth" to be discovered, or that there are various "truths" depending on the context or who is involved.

These assumptions will shape the research from beginning to end.

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Ontology is a branch of philosophy concerned with the global nature of what things are.

When you ask about the nature of something or the principles underlying something, you are

some ontological assumptions about what is being researched for example, that there is a "truth" to be discovered, or that there are various "truths" depending on the context or who is involved. These assumptions will shape the research from beginning to end.

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Ontology is a branch of philosophy concerned with the global nature of what things are. When you ask about the nature of something or the principles underlying something, you are asking ontological questions. For instance, you can ask what exists and what categories does the existence belong to: What is culture? From what perspectives has it been studied? What subjects is culture related to?

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Opportunity sampling

It is utilizing the persons present for sampling at the time of the study and complying with the necessary requirements of the study.

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Panel study

A type of longitudinal survey design that examines the same people over time, enabling researchers to identify and describe any changes that occur between each study. An example of a panel study is to administer a survey to online students at the onset of their program on their perceptions, opinions, beliefs, and attitudes about learning at a distance and then administer the survey again to the same students upon program completion. This will help the researcher to determine actual changes in student perceptions, opinions, beliefs, and attitudes from the start of the program until completion.

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Participants

If qualitative research is conducted on humans, they are called "participants" in contrast to "subjects" in quantitative research. The word 'participants' describes the role such individuals play for the research process. As participants, they have an active role in generating themes and allowing the researcher to extract assertions based on the participants' perceptions and experiences. A researcher relies on participants to drive the research process since the researcher cannot start the process with a bias of a possible outcome.

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Peer Review

Peer review is the use of learners as sources of information, and interactants for each other in such a way that learners assume roles and responsibilities normally taken on by a formally trained teacher, tutor or editor in commenting on and critiquing each other's drafts in both written and oral formats in the process of writing.

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Formal Peer review occurs when you send your work out for publication consideration in a peer reviewed journal or when you apply to present at a conference. The reviewers, experts in the field, will evaluate your work based on their knowledge of the subject and the guidelines of the journal or conference. You can expect to get feedback on your work to help you improve it, if necessary, or better prepare it for publication in your chosen journal or conference proceedings. We can engage in Informal peer review by asking our colleagues in the field to review our work before sending it out for publication consideration.

Cindy Gunn

American University of Sharjah, UAE

reviewed journal or when you apply to present at a conference. The reviewers, experts in the field, will evaluate your work based on their knowledge of the subject and the guidelines of the journal or conference. You can expect to get feedback on your work to help you improve it, if necessary, or better prepare it for publication in your chosen journal or conference proceedings. We can engage in Informal peer review by asking our colleagues in the field to review our work before sending it out for publication consideration.

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Phenomenology

An approach whereby one attempts to comprehend the consideration under scrutiny from the perspective of another.

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Pilot study

An isolated dummy run enacting the data collection tool e.g. the survey questionnaire, the interview protocol to evaluate the feasibility of the data collection tool before the full-scale study is put into practice or conducted.

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Population

The subjects of a particular study or research which share common characteristics or traits.

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Positivistic research

Positivistic research treats the study of social behaviour the same as natural science whereby research is taken to be value-free and objectivity is able to be achieved. Positivistic research believes that by manipulating and controlling variables, absolute truth can be reached.

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Pragmatism

A particular stance in mixed methods at the interface between philosophy and methodology.

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Praxis

The application of theory to practice.

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Predatory journal

The term "predatory journal" was coined in 2010 by American librarian Jeffrey Beall to describe unscrupulous and dishonest open access publishers who were publishing articles with little or no real peer review. Beall also published a list of journals that he considered predatory. However, his list is no longer being updated. A major characteristic of a predatory journal is that it charges publication and/or review fees to authors without providing the editorial support that is characteristic of legitimate journals.

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Primary research

publication and/or review fees to authors without providing the editorial support that is characteristic of legitimate journals.

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Primary research

Primary research is a kind of research that is carried out first-hand by the researcher. Primary signifies first, preliminary, original, basic. Primary research may use qualitative or quantitative research designs and data collection methods.

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Primary trait scale/rubric

Primary trait analysis is a way for teachers to specify the exact criteria against which they will judge student work. The work will be scored so that better or worse performance on a given task can be judged, and the teacher can focus on feedback, student revisions and attention to specific aspects of writing for example.

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A primary trait scale or rubric is the exact criteria against which you are going to analyze/judge your data.

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Probability

The relative possibility that an event will occur.

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Probability sampling

This is any method of sampling which ensures random selection. A procedure must be set up whereby any member of the population being researched must have an equal opportunity of being selected. The clearest example of this method would be drawing the short straw approach.

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Probability sampling is when you use a random selection. For example, when you choose students for a study and you use a computer to choose them.

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Problem statement

A concise description of an issue will be addressed for research purposes.

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In research this refers to one or two sentences that briefly outline the topic that will be addressed in a study. A problem statement focuses on the core essentials of a problem but should allow room for development and exploration. It should avoid being too narrow in scope.

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Privacy protection

As a researcher, you must protect your participants' privacy at all costs. As they allow you to research them, they trust that the information about them will not be able to be accessed by others. Some ways to do this is to assign numbers to individuals and to align all data to such

Privacy protection

As a researcher, you must protect your participants' privacy at all costs. As they allow you to research them, they trust that the information about them will not be able to be accessed by others. Some ways to do this is to assign numbers to individuals and to align all data to such numbers. Privacy should be addressed in the letters of assent and consent.

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Psychometric research

Psychometrics is the study of psychological measurement that includes the measurement of knowledge, abilities, attitudes and personality traits. It is concerned with the differences between individuals. Psychometric research involves two major areas: The construction of valid and reliable instruments and procedures for measurement and the development and refinement of theoretical approaches to measurement.

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Psychometric research involves psychological measures of abilities, attitudes, knowledge and so on to determine differences between people.

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Publication mill

This is a semi-derogatory term for a publishing house which accepts a large number of submissions, with the intention of selling small print runs. It should not be confused with vanity publishing, where the author pays to be published, and where there is no editorial process at all. Even so, publishing mills offer limited editorial support, and the final products have little, if any, academic standing.

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Purposive sampling

Selective type of sampling in research is where subjects or respondents in a study are not representative of the population. Silverman (2005) explains that in current practice, purposive sampling is also termed as theoretical sampling.

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Qualitative data collection methods

Qualitative data collection methods are processes that provide researchers with options to accumulate data on a topic of interest; the nature of the problem described determines whether the data collection process will best be investigated when collecting descriptive, narrative, or non-numerical data from the field (see field research). Gathering information, through observation, structured or unstructured interviews, questionnaires, print or electronic documents, archived records, audio- or videotapes, maps, visuals, photographs, artifacts, field notes, must be done ethically, objectively, and professionally. The data collected whether through participant or non-participant involvement, must be related to the understanding of the topic, must be recorded and protocol-bound, and must assist the researcher in the quest for in-depth understanding of the phenomenon at hand.

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Qualitative Research

In qualitative research, investigators begin the process with a question in mind. The question should be stated as unbiased as possible since the participants will be the sources of answering the question. Researchers identify participants who are able to answer the RQ (research question) by using a rigorous research methodology process. Data collection methods can be interviews, observations, surveys, and more. In the data analysis process, researchers carefully identify themes that can be observed in their data. Researchers triangulate data to verify arising and emergent themes. Based on their themes, researchers can then generate assertions that answer the research question. There are a number of defined research methodologies available for qualitative research allowing for rigorous, generalizable, and replicable studies. Some examples are case studies, ethnographies, grounded theory, phenomenology, and action research.

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Quantitative data collection methods

Quantitative methods emphasize objective measurements and the statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data collected through polls, questionnaires, and surveys or by manipulating pre-existing statistical data using computational techniques.

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Quantitative research

Quantitative research deals with numbers, logic and keeping an objective stance. Quantitative research is not a critical process but reports facts and figures in a systematic narrative way.

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Quasi experiment

A Quasi experiment is a method to study a causal relationship; however, unlike a true experiment, the research subjects are not randomly assigned to the experimental and/or control groups; the subject groups usually used in a study tend to have occurred naturally. The method enables the researcher to design a process to collect and analyze data to infer possible causal explanations to the dilemma.

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Questionnaire

Questionnaires are designed to collect data which can be analyzed through quantitative means.

They are typically close-ended, in that there is a limited number of answers to choose from. In this sense, questionnaires are distinguished from interviews in that interviews are typically looking for more qualitative data. Interviews can complement questionnaires by giving context to questionnaire findings and questionnaires and support data derived from interviews by providing a qualitative framework for the interview results.

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Quota

It is a part of the given allowance.

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Quota sampling

Quota

It is a part of the given allowance.

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Quota sampling

This is a research method that uses non-probability sampling. It is best used with sample audiences that are known to display a high degree of homogeneity, and it uses a limited sample from a population that is known to have similar characteristics. The results are then generalized to the whole population.

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R

R is a statistical software that incorporates and relies on writing programmes to obtain the results of statistical tests. It has the advantage over other software in that scripts can be written to search for particular features in data e.g. text features in corpus analyses.

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Random sampling

This refers to the technique whereby a subset of a sample population is established entirely at random. So, for example, in a sample population of 1000, a random sample is created by drawing 100 names by lot. Every member of the total population then has exactly the same probability of being chosen.

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Ranking

A given place/spot which is selected through certain criteria.

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A research method in which the researcher uses a series of questions to create a hierarchy of priorities; as in the frequency of use of lexis.

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Reference

A reference is a resource a researcher may use to gather information. The resource must include the complete publication evidence so that the researcher acknowledges the source through citation in-text and documenting the publication information at the end of the research report. Gathering information from a reference may mean using print or electronic based sources, such as a book, e-book, journal, e-journal, newspaper, magazine, web-based, audio or video-based, people-based, and/or artifact-based resources.

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Reflexivity

The word reflexive is used to describe a deeper level of reflection which explores the motives of the researcher as well as his or her values and how these are expressed in terms of the subject of the research, methodologies used and the findings established.

Dara Tafazoli

Reflexivity

The word reflexive is used to describe a deeper level of reflection which explores the motives of the researcher as well as his or her values and how these are expressed in terms of the subject of the research, methodologies used and the findings established.

Dara Tafazoli

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Reliability

Reliability is a research term which refers to the stability or uniformity of a research study and its ability to consistently replicate the results of the research. A correlation coefficient is used to assess the measure of reliability. If a test is reliable, it should have a high positive correlation. External and Internal reliability are two kinds of reliabilities in any research. External reliability refers to the degree a measure varies from one use to another. Internal reliability measures the consistency of results across items within a test; a measure of the test within itself.

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Replication

In science and when conducting research, replication is meant to be the repetition of the exact experimental circumstances, conditions and states of the original experiment so that the effectiveness of the experiment and its consistency do not show any difference in its results. This is done so that confidence in the experiment is at its highest level.

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Representative sample

It is the representativeness of the sample and how well it reflects the target population of the study. (The target population are the group of people the study would like to make a claim about.)

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Research

Research is a detailed and systematic investigation not limited to the study of materials so as to establish facts and reach new conclusions based on the data/information found.

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Research engagement

People may either engage with or in research. Engagement with research may take the form of reading published research or attending research talks. Engaging in research usually consists of doing research.

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Research findings

A researcher needs to show how research findings answer his/her research questions and what implications research findings have for researchers and contexts within the same field of study. Depending on the research type, researchers should delineate their research findings objectively and clearly. For example, if a researcher has implemented quantitative methods, he/she may use charts, tables, diagrams and graphs to portray the findings clearly.

Suhair Al Alami

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implications research findings have for researchers and contexts within the same field of study. Depending on the research type, researchers should delineate their research findings objectively and clearly. For example, if a researcher has implemented quantitative methods, he/she may use charts, tables, diagrams and graphs to portray the findings clearly.

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Research instrument

Research instruments are measurement tools designed to obtain data on a topic of interest from research subjects. For example, questionnaires, surveys, tests, or interviews.

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Research literacy

Research literacy can be defined as the knowledge, skills, attitudes and beliefs required to engage with and in research. Knowledge and skills may involve the technical competence to ask research questions, design research instruments, gather and analyse data, and disseminate findings. Certain knowledge and skills are also required in order for someone to critically engage with research. Research literacy also involves appropriate attitudes and beliefs in relation to research. These involve conceptions of what research is and what it entails.

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Research methods

Research methods are the different investigation techniques used to discover a solution or research a problem. They are the strategies used in the research.

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Research question

A research question is an answerable inquiry into a specific issue or concern and is also the initial step in research projects. Writing a good research question contributes to conducting a reliable research project. It is essential therefore that researchers decide what they want to know about a specific issue, translate what they aim to know into a question, make sure that the question is measurable, and ensure that the question is not too narrow or too broad.

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Research paradigm

The interlocking web of a researcher's ontological, epistemological, methodological and axiological beliefs.

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Respondents

The subjects or participants of a study, investigation and/or research. This term is used primarily with questionnaires and/or surveys.

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Response rate

Completion rate, Return rate

The number of people who actually answered a particular questionnaire, divided by the number of people that were asked to answer it. The response rate is expressed as a percentage.

Peter Davidson

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Retrospective interview

Completion rate, Return rate

The number of people who actually answered a particular questionnaire, divided by the number of people that were asked to answer it. The response rate is expressed as a percentage.

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Retrospective interview

A retrospective interview looks backwards and examines outcomes that were established at the start of a study.

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When a researcher interviews subjects about past events. Often used in research to determine research subjects' perceptions for comparison to actual results.

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Rubric

A rubric is a scoring or evaluation tool used to assess and judge the quality of students' performance, using a set of guidelines. A rubric contains assessment criteria, usually presented in the form of a table with standards that can be used by teachers when marking student work and by students to help them guide their responses. A rubric may include the following: the general expectations of the requirements of the assignment; the criteria or descriptors of assessment ordered in levels of the quality of the work from excellent to poor; and the points or marks a student can receive based on the levels of the quality of the work they present.

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Sample

In research a sample is a sub-set of a larger population that is used to represent the entire group as a whole. A sample can be a group of people, objects, or items. The sample should be representative of the population to ensure that researchers can generalize the findings from the research sample to the entire population. Researchers use samples because it is not very practical to try to study every member of a particular population because the number is often too large.

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Sample design

It is a framework to decide the criteria for selecting the sample.

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Sampling error

This is the difference that occurs between the statistics generated from an entire population, the parameters, and from a sample of that population. A sampling error can be countered by using a probabilistic model of the sample and calculating the estimated margin of error.

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Sampling technique

In most cases a researcher cannot collect all the relevant data which exists, and which could help in answering the research question. There may be just too much data to handle within the parameters of the research project. Therefore, the researcher will often, if not always, have to acquire a sub-set or sample of the data. The manner in which it is decided which sub-set to acquire is referred to as data sampling.

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In most cases a researcher cannot collect all the relevant data which exists, and which could help in answering the research question. There may be just too much data to handle within the parameters of the research project. Therefore, the researcher will often, if not always, have to acquire a sub-set or sample of the data. The manner in which it is decided which sub-set to acquire is referred to as data sampling.

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Scaffolding

A scaffold is a structure used to support the construction of a building. It provides support when the longest ladders are not enough. When the internal structure of the building is complete the scaffold is removed and the building stands on its own. Educational scaffolding is a way to think about supporting learning practice. The job of the teacher is to scaffold (support) students so that they can do/practice what they could not do on their own and then give them enough practice with the performance so that they can internalize it (carry it out without having to think through every step) and perform the task without support.

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Scholarly publishing

A publication which publishes double blind peer reviewed papers reporting on academic research of interest to the community of scholars.

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Scholarship

A characteristic involving being well read and also being able to use such knowledge to create convincing arguments in the scholar's field of interest. Scholarship requires the ability to critique as well as assemble new concepts and skillfully present them to peers for review and comment.

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Secondary research

Secondary research involves collecting, summarizing and synthesizing existing (or primary) research.

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Selective reduction

In qualitative research the mass of data must be organized and meaningfully reduced and reconfigured. Selective data reduction is the first step in this process as the researcher decides which data are singled out for description according to clear principles of selectivity involving deductive and inductive analysis.

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In research, data reduction is the transformation of information into a corrected, ordered, and simplified form. Selective reduction is when you use specific criteria for that reduction.

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Semi-structured interview

An open-ended type of questioning where a set of questions are framed before the conduct of the inquiry. This type of interview also requires an interview guide that is subjected to pilot testing in order to supplement the questioning and probing.

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Semi-structured interview

An open-ended type of questioning where a set of questions are framed before the conduct of the inquiry. This type of interview also requires an interview guide that is subjected to pilot testing in order to supplement the questioning and probing.

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A semi-structured interview is one of three types of interviews used in educational research with the other two being structured and unstructured. Semi structured interviews are the most commonly used in our field. They are qualitative in nature. Researchers using this type of interview are first required to develop an interview protocol which is a list of questions or topics that every participant is asked during their interviews. During the interview, however, there is a certain degree of flexibility in that researchers may follow up on certain key statements made by the participant if they deem it important to the goals of their study and to the data collection.

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Sequential data collection

Sequential data collection/research design is a typical design employed under mixed methods research. Sequential data collection means one set of data (e.g. quantitative data) is collected and its results and analysis may then lead to another type of data (e.g. qualitative data) being collected at a later stage. The rationale for employing such a design is to minimise the weaknesses of collecting only one type of data.

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Snowball sampling

It is where the participants are recruited from among a group of people we know. Then we ask them to recruit more people and so on. It is like sending an email to a colleague and asking them to send the email to other colleagues. Like a snowball the sample continues to grow.

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Sociolinguistic interview

The sociolinguistic interview generally starts with informal free conversation which is followed by formal language tasks that gradually get difficult for the interviewee. While the aim of the free conversation is to elicit natural speech, the formal tasks focus on eliciting specific data that usually does not occur during informal conversations. This technique is often used in language variation studies.

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This is a method of data research, frequently used in sociolinguistic studies. The scholar conducting the research acts as the interviewer, and the informant is the interviewee. Different methods can be used, but the interviewers frequently attempt to relax the interviewees to the point where they use a casual style of speech. The very formality of the setting, however, may act against loss of self-consciousness.

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SPSS

SPSS is a statistical software that allows users to input variables and data. After this input, users can conduct a range of statistical procedures including statistical significance tests, correlation and regression analysis. Users can also obtain tabular data output as well as a range of graphs and charts that show relationships between variables.

Lee McCallum

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Stakeholder

A stakeholder is someone who has a stake in an activity, that is, anyone who has an interest or will be affected by the outcome of an effort. Some stakeholders have a higher stake (that is, they will be more effected) by the outcome of an activity than others. For example, the student and the Minister of Education are both stakeholders in the education of the student, however the stakes (the importance of the outcome) will be much higher and much more immediate for the student than for the Minister of Education. Similarly, the school principal or headmaster will have a higher stake in the students' education than the mayor of the town. Yes, the mayor has a stake in the students' education because having up-and-coming students who will be productive, engaged citizens of the town is a potential benefit for the town, but it is the principal who is more directly affected, who has the greater responsibility, and has a higher stake in student success.

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Standard deviation

Standard deviation is a statistical procedure to show how dispersed the measurements are from the mean as the point of reference. The higher the standard deviation is, the larger the dispersion will be. To calculate the standard deviation, both raw scores and mean scores can be used. Once the variance has been calculated, its second root produces the standard deviation value.

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Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis consists of the scientific methods of data collection and the discovery of patterns and trends in it. This includes summarizing the data, finding key measures of location, calculating measures of spread, making future predictions based on past behavior and testing an experiment's hypothesis.

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Statistical bias

The statistical difference between an estimator's (a rule for calculating an estimate of a given quantity based on observed data) expected value and the true value of the parameter being estimated is called the Statistical bias. It can be measured with respect to mean or median as estimators. An estimator with zero bias is called unbiased. Otherwise it is considered to be biased.

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Statistical significance

Statistical significance means the researcher is very sure that the result is reliable. A result has statistical significance when the researcher is able to reject the null hypothesis, which is the default assumption that nothing happened or changed. Statistical significance tests help the researcher account for potential sampling errors.

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Stratified sample

Stratified sampling is a probability sampling research method whereby the sample or the population intended to be used in an experiment or a survey is divided into homogeneous or

researcher account for potential sampling errors.

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Stratified sample

Stratified sampling is a probability sampling research method whereby the sample or the population intended to be used in an experiment or a survey is divided into homogeneous or identical non-overlapping groups called strata. Samples of age groups, geographical areas, etc. are examples of such stratification. All of this is done to reduce error in results because of the commonality with the same strata.

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This term refers to a sampling technique in which the researcher sub-divides the total population into different groups, referred to as “strata”. These subsets are then investigated using random sampling.

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Stimulated recall interview

Stimulated recall interviewing is a research technique in which subjects are exposed to a piece of information/stimulus and are later invited to reflect on their thinking during the exposure to it.

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This is a research method whereby the researcher stimulates a reflective commentary of an event that has been recorded. For example, an educational researcher asking a teacher to give a commentary of their thought processes during a lesson usually through the replaying of a video or audio recording of that lesson.

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Structured interview

A quantitative method of research used to conduct survey research. The questions are pre-determined and can be close-ended, open-ended, or both. The interviewer asks the same questions in the same order of each participant and records their responses.

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Subjects

Subjects are persons that are involved in a quantitative research study. Reference to participants means the human beings under study may be part of a quantitative or qualitative research design.

The person is usually selected from a defined population and are part of a sample that reflects the population. The information included in the Methods section of a research report about the subjects includes information about how the subjects were chosen, the sampling procedure used, the descriptors, such as age, sex, religion, grade, ability, and socioeconomic status. A subject of study may be human, a program, an institution, an event, an action, or a behavior.

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Survey

A Survey or questionnaire is an instrument or tool used to gather information that describes things, identifies attitudes or beliefs, and/or describes behaviors. The survey enables the researcher to collect data to test hypotheses or answer research questions; thus, it serves both descriptive qualitative and quantitative research methods and data collection options. The survey type varies depending on the research purpose and is designed accordingly.

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Sustainability

Sustainability is an ongoing process of change; the requirement of a generation that enables them

descriptive qualitative and quantitative research methods and data collection options. The survey type varies depending on the research purpose and is designed accordingly.

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Sustainability

Sustainability is an ongoing process of change; the requirement of a generation that enables them to manipulate and manage their resources, investments, the technological development and institutional change in order to guarantee and enhance the quality of life for both current and future generations' needs and aspirations.

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Tabulation

Tabulation is to take the collected data, perform the statistics (if needed), and put the numbers into a table. Then the researcher must interpret or crosstab the information and infer the relationships to that result. The table must have a Table number and a title, and the rows and columns must be labeled accordingly.

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Teacher beliefs

The conceptions that teachers hold about a variety of things in their professional domain and which they deem to be true. Beliefs may influence teachers' thoughts and practices in a conscious or subconscious manner. With respect to research, teachers may hold beliefs which either facilitate their research engagement or else lead them to perceive research as something alien to their professional identity and practices.

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Teacher research

Teacher research is intentional, systematic and focused investigation of a significant issue to teachers who are actually working with students in a structured environment. Teacher research includes a carefully designed research question, a description of data collection methodology (subjects, techniques, procedures and effort to identify and measure variables identified), data analysis, interpretation, limitations and implications.

Liz England

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Teacher research is an activity driven by questions teachers may have about their practices, students, context or themselves as professionals. These questions may either be answered in a systematic manner typical of some research approaches, or else in much freer ways. At a basic level teacher research involves some element of observation and reflection as a means of arriving at an answer to a question. Teacher research need not follow the formal process that is usually adopted in empirical research and it need not be published or disseminated.

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TESOL Quarterly (TQ)

TESOL Quarterly (TQ) is a TESOL International Association publication, currently published by Wiley-Blackwell. TQ was first published in 1967 and is a quarterly peer-reviewed academic journal that fosters English language teaching research. Authors have a broad range of topics they can research and report about. TQ's readership is also diverse and it includes teachers, researchers, linguists, language professionals and more.

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Theory

The word theory has many meanings in a wide variety of contexts. In academic research a theory is an explanation of how variables interact and the consequences of their interaction. A theory will explain how a phenomenon works but will not necessarily explain why it works. Addressing theory is a fundamental requirement of academic research.

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Think aloud protocol

A Think-aloud protocol is a data elicitation and collection technique in which participants speak aloud any words in their mind as they complete a task. Experts state that think-alouds are theoretically sound and provide a valid source of data about participant thinking.

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TIRF

TIRF, the International Research for English Language Education was officially founded in 1999, under the funding of TESOL Inc (now TESOL International) as a research body for developing knowledge of English Language learning. Since its inception, it has received grants from many entities, like Betty Azar, Sheikh Nahayan (UAE) and others. TIRF has produced top notch research papers and continues to strive for quality development of English language learning.

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Triangulation

A method used in research that combines qualitative and quantitative methods, sometimes called mixed methods. The purpose is to measure and understand different aspects of a phenomenon.

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Triangulation in research basically means using more than one method to collect data on the same topic. Essentially findings from one method are cross-validated by those in another with the aim of achieving greater validity in your research. Triangulation could involve different types of samples as well as methods of data collection. The purpose of triangulation is not solely to cross-validate data but rather to capture different dimensions of the same phenomenon.

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True experimental design research

True Experimental Design Research is a quantitative way to study a cause effect relationship by applying two conditions: the researcher must manipulate the independent variable(s) to observe the effect(s) on the dependent variable(s) and control extraneous variable(s) that may confound or prompt a spurious relationship. Experimental research permits design, treatment, variables and procedure options and addresses reliability and validity needs. Subjects are drawn randomly or at random from representative samples of a population and are assigned to control and experimental groups. The research design is created to explore hypotheses and research questions by treatment comparisons that influence outcome results. Variables are identified and

True Experimental Design Research is a quantitative way to study a cause effect relationship by applying two conditions: the researcher must manipulate the independent variable(s) to observe the effect(s) on the dependent variable(s) and control extraneous variable(s) that may confound or prompt a spurious relationship. Experimental research permits design, treatment, variables and procedure options and addresses reliability and validity needs. Subjects are drawn randomly or at random from representative samples of a population and are assigned to control and experimental groups. The research design is created to explore hypotheses and research questions by treatment comparisons that influence outcome results. Variables are identified and procedures are created based on the investigation purposes.

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T-test

T-test is a parametric test that checks whether the two levels of an independent variable are reliably and significantly different. T-test is often used when there is a categorical independent variable at two levels and one continuous, or interval dependent variable. There are two types of t-tests: independent-samples t-test, with two different groups, and paired-samples t-test, with a single group sampled twice at different time intervals. One major assumption in t-tests is the homogeneity of variances between the two samples.

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Two-way ANOVA

Two-way ANOVA is a statistical procedure used to discover means differences of two independent variables with different levels and their interaction effect on the independent variable. If we have age groups (Young-Adults) and gender (Men-Women) as the independent variables and language learning aptitude as the dependent variable, a two-way ANOVA can inform us about the main effects of each independent categorical variable and their interaction effect on the dependent variable.

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Unbiased

To be unbiased means to show no prejudice for or against something or someone when conducting or reporting research. It also applies to the selection of research subjects and analysis of results in that the research should avoid the effect of any extraneous variables that may unduly sway the results one way or another.

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Unstructured interview

An unstructured interview, sometimes called a non-directive interview or a discovery interview, is a type of interview where questions are not prepared or arranged ahead of time. This type of interview tends to be less formal and is conducted through a type of casual conversation. There is a spontaneous flow of questions that are developed as the interview progresses based on what responses the interviewee is providing. This type of interview is considered a method of qualitative research.

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Validity

Validity in research relates to the degree or how well the research instrument measures what it is supposed to measure. Validity is important in research because it assists the researcher in deciding the type of test to use for what is being measured. Validity is divided into internal and external groups. Internal validity refers to how the findings of the research match reality. However, external validity refers to how the research findings can be effectively replicated or

Validity

Validity in research relates to the degree or how well the research instrument measures what it is supposed to measure. Validity is important in research because it assists the researcher in deciding the type of test to use for what is being measured. Validity is divided into internal and external groups. Internal validity refers to how the findings of the research match reality. However, external validity refers to how the research findings can be effectively replicated or generalized to other situations or environments. Moreover, validity has five basic types: 1. Face Validity where research is based on subjectivity without much of in-depth scientific rationalization. 2. Construct Validity looks at the suitability of the constructed tool to measure what is being studied. 3. Criterion-Related Validity revolves around the comparison and the correlation of test results with another criterion of assessment. 4. Formative Validity is the assessment of the effectiveness of the measurement tool in providing data that can help improve specific aspects of what is being tested. 5. Sampling Validity or content validity is a research tool where important items and a good representative sample is used to measure what is being measured because of the abundance of a very vast content.

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In research, evaluative validity highlights the use of an evaluation framework that helps researchers evaluate the usefulness of the assessments or judgements of the phenomenon studied.

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Variable

Variables are constructs or concepts that are operationally defined and accounted for by value measurements which may include nominal, ordinal, ratio or interval scaling. A variable is studied based on a purpose and on creating a research design and is measured or manipulated by the researcher, linking the theory to empirical outreach.

Classifying variables means they may be single or multivariate markers.

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Variance

Variance is a measure of how scores are spread in a distribution. It is not often used as a stand-alone feature in statistical calculations and is used in some other statistical procedures such as standard deviation. Variance can be calculated using the formula $\sigma^2 = \sum(x - \mu)^2/n$, where σ^2 denotes the variance and μ symbolizes the mean.

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Verbal report

Sometimes called a Think-aloud, a verbal report is an oral account of a person's thoughts and personal experiences. Verbal reports are used as a source of data during the task (think-aloud) or after the task (retrospective). They are conducted following certain principles and procedures.

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Weighted score

A weighted score is essentially an average with greater or lesser weight given to some of the figures. For example, GPA (grade point average) is calculated based on each grade being weighted based on the number of credits in each course. Another example is when a teacher puts

Weighted score

A weighted score is essentially an average with greater or lesser weight given to some of the figures. For example, GPA (grade point average) is calculated based on each grade being weighted based on the number of credits in each course. Another example is when a teacher puts greater weight on certain assessments such as the midterm or final exam.

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A weighted score is the average of a set of numbers, where each set/range carries a different amount of importance.

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